

Pre-conference Workshop (only on registration)

All oral presentations in Civic Suites 1/2

Monday 3 May

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Workshop	09:30	Welcome and Introduction to IVS-ESRI workshop by <u>Douglas Bergersen</u> (IVS3D)	
	09:45	ESRI Tools for Habitat Mapping by <u>Jaime Crandall</u> (ESRI)	
	10:15	IVS Tools for Habitat Mapping by <u>Lindsay Gee</u> (IVS3D)	
Bk	10:45	Tea Break (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)	
Workshop	11:00	Use of the ARC Marine Data Model in the context of Habitat Mapping by <u>Jaime Crandall</u> (ESRI)	
	11:30	IVS-ESRI Habitat Mapping Workflow applied to the NIWA Cook Strait data set by <u>Douglas Bergersen</u> (IVS3D)	
Break	12:00	Lunch Break (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)	
Workshop	13:00	Case Example 1 by <u>Jens Greinhart</u> (Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research)	
	13:40	Case Example 2 by <u>Arne Pallentin</u> (National Institute of Water and Atmospheric Research, NZ)	
	14:20	Case Example 3 by <u>Scott Nichol</u> (Geoscience Australia)	
	15:00	Final Comments and questions by <u>Douglas Bergersen</u> (IVS3D)	
Break	15:30	Tea Break (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)	
	16:00		
Social Event	17:00	Geohab 2010 Icebreaker and Registration 17:00-19:00, Mac's Brewery Bar & Restaurant	

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Tuesday 4 May		
Reg.	08:00	Conference Registration open
Welcome	08:30	Mihimihi (Traditional Maori Welcome)
	08:40	Opening and Welcome
Keynote Chair: Brian Todd	09:00	KEYNOTE ADDRESS: "An Atlas of Ireland's Deep-water Seabed: the preview" by <u>Andy Wheeler</u> , Boris Dorschel, Xavier Monteys and Koen Verbruggen
S1 - Mapping Chair: Brian Todd	09:30	"A picture on the wall: 3D habitat mapping in deep-sea canyons" by <u>Veerle A.I. Huvenne</u> , Doug G. Masson, Paul A. Tyler, Veit Hühnerbach and the ISIS ROV Team
	09:50	STUDENT AWARD: "A system for mapping nearshore, marine habitats on a tight budget" by <u>Kelly C. Kingon</u>
Break	10:10	Tea Break and Posters (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)
S1 - Mapping Metrics Chair: Vaughan Stagpoole	10:50	"Seafloor sediment classification in a tidal inlet channel: The influence of shell debris and seafloor rugosity" by <u>Dietmar Bürk</u> , Martina Heineke, H. Christian Hass, Ralf Vorberg and Rolf Riethmüller
	11:10	"Geo-statistical mapping of sediment composition with application to habitat classification" by David Stephens, <u>Markus Diesing</u> and Roger Coggan
	11:30	"Deep-Water Forage Habitats - The Next Step Forward in Marine Benthic Habitat Mapping?" by <u>H. Gary Greene</u> , J. Vaughn Barrie and Tina Wyllie-Echeverria
	11:50	"Geoacoustic mapping of cold seep habitats along the Hikurangi margin, New Zealand" by <u>Ingo Klaucke</u> , Andrew T. Jones, Wilhelm Weinrebe, David Bowden and C. Jörg Petersen
	12:10	"Seamount habitat mapping on the Condor Bank (Azores, NE Atlantic)" by <u>Fernando Tempera</u> , E. Giacomello, F. Porteiro, A. Martins, I. Bashmachnikov, A. Henriques, J. Nuno Pereira, T. Morato, D. Catarino, R. Santos and G. Menezes
Break	12:30	Lunch Kindly sponsored by IMarest Served in Civic Suite 3 and Foyer

S1 - Mapping Metrics	Chair: David Bowden	13:30	<p align="center">"The role of physical environmental variables in shaping seabed biodiversity patterns"</p> <p align="center">by <u>Roland Pitcher</u>, Nick Ellis, Peter Lawton, Stephen Smith, Chi-Lin Wei, Lew Incze, Michelle Greenlaw, Jess Sameoto, Nick Wolff, Tom Shirley and Gil Rowe</p>
		13:50	<p align="center">"Mapping and Predicting Benthic Habitats, Biological Assemblages, and Biodiversity across the Carnarvon Shelf, Western Australia"</p> <p align="center">by <u>Tara J. Anderson</u>, Andrew Heyward, Scott Nichols, Matthew McArthur, Christine Schoenberg, Jamie Colquhoun, Zhi Huang, Maggie Tran and Brendan Brooke</p>
		14:10	<p align="center">"Multibeam sonar in the deep-sea: can it really tell us much about benthic habitats and fauna?"</p> <p align="center">by <u>David Bowden</u>, Judi Hewitt, Anne-Laure Verdier and Arne Pallentin</p>
		14:30	<p align="center">"Habitat-based assessment of epibenthos using AUV Optical imagery, northwest Australia"</p> <p align="center">by <u>Jamie Colquhoun</u>, Oscar Pizarro, Andrew Heyward, Max Rees, Stefan Williams, Rebecca O'leary and Ben Radford</p>
		14:50	<p align="center">"A GIS analysis of New Zealand's Trawl Footprint"</p> <p align="center">by <u>Jenny Black</u> and Ray Wood</p>
S1 - Mapping Metrics	Chair: Andrew Heap	15:10	<p>Tea Break and Posters (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)</p>
		15:40	<p align="center">"A geospatial approach to coral reef geomorphology"</p> <p align="center">by <u>Javier Leon</u>, Colin Woodroffe, Kevin Parnell and Scott Smithers</p>
S1 - Mapping Metrics	Chair: Andrew Heap	16:00	<p align="center">"A comparison of fish diversity estimates made by stereo-video systems and traps at depths ranging from 50 to 900m"</p> <p align="center">by <u>Vincent Zintzen</u>, Clive Roberts, Andrew Stewart, Marti J. Anderson and Euan Harvey</p>
		16:20	<p align="center">"Application of an Integrated GIS and 4D Visualisation Tool Kit to the NIWA Cook Strait Data Set"</p> <p align="center">by <u>Douglas Bergersen</u>, Moe Doucet, Lindsay Gee and Robin Smith</p>
		16:40	<p align="center">"Making Technology Transparent - A key to better science is spending more time studying the data than collecting it"</p> <p align="center">by <u>Francois Leroy</u></p>
Bk		17:00	<p>Break</p>
Special Meeting	Mark Costello	17:10	<p>Special Glossary Meeting:</p> <p>"Towards an international marine geo-bio-ecological glossary"</p> <p>(See details in General Information, p. 17)</p>
S6 - ATLAS	Chair: Peter Harris	17:40	<p>Special ATLAS Session:</p> <p>"Geohab Atlas of seafloor geomorphic features and benthic habitats"</p> <p>(See details in General Information, p. 17)</p> <p>(~ 90 min)</p>
		19:10	

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Wednesday 5 May	
Reg.	08:00 Conference Registration open
Keynote	08:30 KEYNOTE ADDRESS: "Credibility of sonar Backscatter Strength measurement, modelling and inversion" by <u>Xavier Lurton</u> and Jean-Marie Augustin
S2 - Statistical Analysis Chair: Vanessa Lucieer	09:00 "Can oceanographic conditions explain species distribution patterns on the Chatham Rise and Challenger Plateau" by <u>Kathryn Julian</u> , Tanya J. Compton and David Bowden
	09:20 "Some issues in predicting biodiversity using spatially modelled covariates" by <u>Hideyasu Shimadzu</u> , Scott D. Foster and Ross Darnell
	09:40 "Spatial predictability of species diversity and abundance of epimacrobenthos in turbid nearshore using bathymetric LiDAR" by <u>Antoine Collin</u> , Bernard Long and Philippe Archambault
	10:00 "Modelling species distributions: the application of predicted habitat models to define demersal fish distributions" by <u>Cordelia H. Moore</u> , Ben Radford, Euan S. Harvey and Kimberly Van Niel
Break	Tea Break and Posters (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)
S2 - Statistical Analysis Chair: Vladimir Kostylev	10:50 "Towards Automated Classification of Benthic Environments using Rugosity, Slope and Aspect from Bathymetric Stereo Image Reconstructions" by <u>Ariell Friedman</u> (STUDENT AWARD), Oscar Pizarro and Stefan Williams
	11:10 "Object based segmentation of multibeam backscatter data: methods for spatial analysis of shallow coastal seabeds, South Eastern Tasmania, Australia" by <u>Vanessa Lucieer</u> , Nicole Hill and Neville Barrett
	11:30 "Deriving "mappable" biological assemblages from underwater footage using classification tree models" by <u>Genoveva Gonzalez-Mirelis</u> (STUDENT AWARD), and Mats Lindegarth
	11:50 "Image-based habitat classification and analysis using generative models" by <u>Oscar Pizarro</u> , Stefan Williams, Jamie Colquhoun and Cordelia Moore
	12:10 "Automated delineation of acoustic themes from Multibeam backscatter data for seafloor characterization, Tapuae Marine Reserve, NZ" by <u>Alexandre C.G. Schimel</u> , Yuri Rzhano, Luciano Fonseca, Larry Mayer, Terry R. Healy and Dirk Immenga
Break	12:30 Lunch Kindly sponsored by Gardline Environmental Served in Civic Suite 3 and Foyer

S2	S3 - Geo-Bio Interaction Chair: Ian Wright	13:30	"Predicting Groups of Species: application of finite mixture models to species prediction" by Piers K. Dunstan, Scott D. Foster and Ross Darnell
		13:50	"Environmental classifications, acoustic remote assessment and ecosystem valuing" by Judi E. Hewitt, Joanne Ellis, David Bowden and Ian Tuck
		14:10	"Diversity in benthic habitats and sediments at Great Barrier Island, New Zealand" by Tuan Meng Lee (STUDENT AWARD), Kala Sivaguru, Roger Grace, Timothy J. Langlois and Mark J. Costello
		14:30	"Geomorphological characterisation of cold water corals habitats (Bay of Biscay, NE Atlantic)" by Jean-Francois Bourillet, Thierry Schmitt, Alessandra Savini, Brigitte Guillaumont and Sophie Arnaud-Haond
		14:50	"The Catalan submarine canyon heads, NW Mediterranean Sea: coupling seafloor morphology and biological diversity" by Miquel Canals, Galderic Lastras, David Amblas, Ben De Mol and "Euroleón" Cruise Shipboard Party
Break		15:10	Tea Break and Posters (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)
S3 - Geo-Bio Interaction Chair: Judi Hewitt		15:40	"GIS-Mapping of Marine Benthic Habitats using Expert-based and Statistical Methodologies" by Roland Pesch, Susanne Ranft, Marc Busch and Winfried Schroder
		16:00	"Relationships between seabed assemblages in the Gulf of Maine and their physical environment using Random Forests" by Peter Lawton, Stephen J. Smith, Lewis S. Incze, Michelle E. Greenlaw, Nicholas H. Wolff, Jessica Sameoto, Roland Pitcher, Nick Ellis
		16:20	"Geostatistical and landscape analysis of fine-scale eelgrass (<i>Zostera marina</i>) habitat patterns" by Jeffrey Barrell (STUDENT AWARD) and Jon Grant
		16:40	"Dynamics of benthic patch structure across two seasons in a coastal embayment" by Zhi Huang, Lynda Radke and Matthew Mearthur
		17:00	"Physical controls on deep-water coral communities on the George V margin, East Antarctica" by Alexandra L. Post, P.E. O'brien, R.J. Beaman and M.J. Riddle
Break		17:20	Break
Social Event		18:30	Barbecue 18:30-22:00, Royal Port Nicholson Yatch Club

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Thursday 6 May

Reg.	08:00	Conference Registration open
Keynote	08:30	KEYNOTE ADDRESS: "Habitat as a proxy for biodiversity: how can seamount classification systems aid the scientific design of marine protected areas" by <u>Malcolm R. Clark</u> , Ashley A. Rowden, Les Watling, John M. Guinotte and Craig R. Smith
S3 - Geo-Bio Interactions Chair: Bernard Pelletier	09:00	"Environmental - biological covariance in the soft sediments surrounding Lord Howe Island" by <u>Matthew McArthur</u> , Hideyasu Shimadzu and Brendan Brooke
	09:20	"The Influence of Physical Parameters on Benthic Communities – A Case Study in the Gulf of Finland, the Baltic Sea" by <u>Anna-Leena Downie</u> and Anu M. Kaskela
	09:40	"Spatial prediction of demersal fish habitat suitability from remotely-sensed observation and hydroacoustic datasets" by <u>Jacquomo Monk</u> , D. Ierodiaconou, A. Bellgrove, E. Harvey, A. Rattray, L. Laurenson and G. Quinn
	10:00	"Quantifying trawling impacts on deep-sea ecosystems using ROV video and scanning-sonar data" by <u>Maeva Gauthier</u> , S. Kim Juniper, J. Vaughn Barrie, Rosaline R. Canessa and James A. Boutillier
Break	10:20	Tea Break and Posters (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)
S4 - Vulnerable Habitat Chair: Miquel Canais	10:50	"Identifying ecologically and biologically significant deepwater habitat" by <u>Nicholas J. Bax</u> and Alan Williams
	11:10	"Using GIS Models to Delimit Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem (VME) Boundaries in the Northwest Atlantic Regulatory Area (NRA)" by <u>Andrew T. Cogswell</u> , Ellen L.R. Kenchington and Camille G. Lirette
	11:30	"Predictive cold-water coral habitat mapping in the Western Mediterranean Sea" by <u>Ben De Mol</u> , David Amblas, Miquel Canais, Galderic Lastras, Anna Sanchez, Antonio Calafat, and Darwin Cd178, Euroleon and Hermesione Shipboard Party
	11:50	"The alkaline hydrothermal field of the Prony Bay, Southern New Caledonia" by <u>Bernard Pelletier</u> and Claude E. Payri
	12:10	"Seabed habitats of the Beaufort Sea Shelf (Canadian Arctic)" by <u>Vladimir E. Kostylev</u> , Kerstin Jerosch and Steve Blasco
Break	12:30	Lunch Break and Posters (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)

S5 - National Programmes	Chair: Nic Bax	13:30	"Mapping habitat and biological diversity in coastal ecosystems: Bay of Islands, New Zealand" by <u>Mark Morrison</u> , & the NIWA Ocean Survey 20/20 Project Team
		13:50	"Mesophotic Coral Ecosystems of Puerto Rico" by <u>Roy A. Armstrong</u> and Hanumant Singh
		14:10	"Seabed mapping for Australia's energy security" by <u>Andrew D. Heap</u> , Rachel Przeslawski, Scott Nichol, Lynda Radke, Chris Battershill and Stephen Whalan
		14:30	"Mapping and modelling spatial distribution of important nature types such as kelp forest, sea grass beds and shell sand, procedures and results from a national mapping program in Norway with focus on the Skagerrak region" by <u>Eli Rinde</u> , J. Gitmark, H. Christie, W. Eikrem, H. Olsen, R. Bøe, H. Steen and T. Bodvin
		14:50	"Phanerogame meadows: a characteristic habitat of the Mediterranean shelf. Examples from the Tyrrhenian Sea" by <u>Silvana D'angelo</u> and Andrea Fiorentino
Break		15:10	Tea Break and Posters (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)
S5 - National Prog.	Chair: Gary Greene	15:40	"Habitat Mapping in Aitutaki, Cook Islands" by <u>Ashishika Sharma</u> (STUDENT AWARD), Jens Krüger, Satesh Kumar, Chris Roelfsema and Ngere George
		16:00	"ZoNeCo: a multidisciplinary approach to Marine Habitats in New Caledonia" by <u>Yves Lafoy</u> , A. Rivaton and D Buisson
		16:20	"Mapping and modelling seabed nature-types in Norway's MAREANO programme – lessons learned" by <u>Margaret F.J. Dolan</u> , Pål Buhl-Mortensen, Kim Picard, Terje Thorsnes, Sigrid Elvenes, Valérie K. Bellec, Lene Buhl-Mortensen and Reidulv Bøe
Break		16:40	Break
Discussion		17:10	Wrap-up discussion (~1h) AGM

Friday 7 May

FIELD TRIP :
Discover faults, rocks, food and wine

07:50	Please assemble near the Wellington Town Hall The Tranzit coach will be parked in Wakefield Street, outside the Wellington Town Hall, opposite the West Plaza Hotel.
08:00	Depart Wellington, driving past the Parliament Buildings and “The Beehive” before heading north on the motorway that travels alongside the Wellington Fault (optional stop on the Wellington Fault outcrop). After skirting Wellington Harbour, we travel up the Hutt River valley, then across the spectacular Rimutaka Hill Road (summit 550 m) to the Wairarapa region, with stops to inspect the sights.
10:15	Meet our Zest guide at the entrance to the Martinborough Wine Village, then visit Martinborough Vineyard – one of the founding vineyards and wineries in the district – meet the viticulturist and/or winemaker and taste the wine’s terroir in the glass, especially the Pinot Noir for which the district is renowned.
12:00	Lunch at Coney Wines, a winery and cafe about 10 minutes south of Martinborough Village. Relax and refuel with good food and wine.
13:45	Depart Coney Wines and travel to the South Coast of the North Island, to walk up Putangirua Stream (cut through ancient gravel layers) to see the striking Putangirua Pinnacles landforms (you might recognise them as a scene stealer in “Lord of the Rings”).
16:00	Leave the coast and return to Featherston via the East-West Access Road with glimpses of Lake Wairarapa, and back to Wellington over the Rimutaka Hill Road
18:00 (approx)	Arrive back in Wellington, at the Town Hall (Wakefield Street)